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ConcePTION

WP1 – Moving beyond pregnancy registries to enhance our understanding of disease-related pregnancy outcomes, medication use and safety of use during pregnancy

D1.7 Submitted manuscript of a guidance document outlining lessons learned for conducting drug utilization and medication safety studies based on secondary data sources in pregnancy using the ConcePTION pipeline

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Abstract

An objective in the IMI ConcePTION project was to generate timely and reliable evidence on maternal, pregnancy and infant outcomes and breastfeeding following medication use during pregnancy by using routinely collected data from existing European health data sources. We provide guidance on performing medication safety studies in pregnancy using these data sources, based on lessons learned from the work on five demonstration projects in ConcePTION.

During the project, data analysts worked with the demonstration project study teams to provide data science input and facilitate the transition to common data models, data characterization and a ConcePTION pipeline. Algorithms to identify pregnancy episodes and disease phenotypes were developed, scripted and run across available data sources. Subsequently drug utilization studies and safety studies were piloted in selected demonstration projects.

During the implementation of the protocols and analytical plans, the study teams had to overcome several data-related and technical hurdles. A list of ten challenges that need to be overcome using the ConcePTION common data model and pipeline was compiled, along with suggested methods for addressing them.

Implementing these recommendations will enable future research to achieve greater efficiency, accuracy, relevance, and impact.

Introduction

Many pregnant women take at least one medication for treatment of acute or chronic disorders during their pregnancy and with increasing maternal age and co-morbidities these proportions are increasing (Madley-Dowd et al, 2024; Fortinguerra et al., 2023). Strong evidence on pregnancy outcomes, including perinatal and long-term effects, following medication use during pregnancy is paramount. Innovative methods to generate reliable evidence for new medications in a timely manner are needed to enhance our understanding of disease-related pregnancy outcomes and the benefits and risks of medication use in pregnancy.

The aim of the ConcePTION project was to build an ecosystem that can generate robust evidence on medication safety in pregnancy. One of the aims of the ConcePTION project was to identify and evaluate existing data sources that can be used to study medications in pregnancy. Whilst not initially designed for the purpose of studying medications in pregnancy, these secondary data sources can often be linked to provide valuable evidence in a fast and cost-effective way (de Jonge et al., 2015). Multinational pharmaco-epidemiological studies in pregnancy face unique challenges due to differing

populations, healthcare systems, data sources and regulatory environments in addition to national differences in defining outcomes (Euro-Peristat, 2022), Rigorous methods and strong collaborations must be created to be successful. Guidelines exist for the performance of such studies (FDA 2019; EMA EnCePP 2023; ICH M14), but lack details on how to identify, access, link and combine the right data sources to provide timely and adequate information on medication exposure and medication safety during pregnancy. They do not fully address the scientific and methodological challenges of generating evidence for the pregnant population.

As a research and innovation platform, ConcePTION developed a fair data catalogue (deliverable D7.7; <https://www.imi-conception.eu/results/deliverables/>), a common data model (Thurin et al, 2021) and data quality indicators (INSIGHT; Hoxhaj et al., in preparation) as well as a pipeline for systematic data transformation using a distributed approach that was tested in five innovative demonstration studies. These demonstration projects were performed covering specific diseases and treatments using secondary data sources to tackle challenges in the use of such data and to provide guidance to future researchers undertaking similar studies. The scientific findings of the five demonstration studies are reported separately. (deliverable D1.6; <https://www.imi-conception.eu/results/deliverables/>).

Methods

In the first phase of the ConcePTION project a mapping exercise was conducted regarding possible data sources for the demonstration projects. A reference document “The ConcePTION Data Source Catalogue” was created and published to guide the selection of data sources (deliverables D1.1 and D7.7; <https://www.imi-conception.eu/results/deliverables/>). A second step was the identification and definition of core evidence elements for generating medications safety evidence for pregnancy using population-based data. This document has also been published, providing researchers with common definitions of elements necessary to produce robust study results (D1.2; <https://www.imi-conception.eu/results/deliverables/>).

Five innovative demonstration projects with specific methodological challenges regarding medication in pregnancy were envisaged to test the ConcePTION pipeline.

1. **“Methods for controlling by indication for prescriptions: application to medications for neuropathic pain.”** EUPAS43385 this study uses data from six European countries to look at methodological issues in confounding by indication for drugs used for neuropathic pain and other indications. The second part of the protocol describes a drug utilization study of drugs used to treat

neuropathic pain among women of childbearing age. Finally, it includes a safety study focusing on pregabalin and gabapentin use during pregnancy and associated adverse pregnancy outcomes including major congenital anomalies.

2. **“Exposure to SSRI/SNRI and depression in pregnancy and long-term childhood outcomes: the effect of modifying factors.”** EUPAS43416 this study aims to validate algorithms to identify maternal depression, neurodevelopmental outcomes (Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder, Autism Spectrum Disorder, Intellectual Development Disorders and Delayed Infant Development), and breastfeeding in healthcare data sources. The second part of the protocol addresses the use of selected antidepressants, before, during, and after pregnancy. Finally, a drug safety study was planned to assess the risk for adverse neurodevelopmental outcomes in infants exposed in utero to antidepressants.

3. **“Novel statistics to handle rare diseases and small sample sizes using Bayesian techniques: Application to MS in pregnancy.”** EUPAS43420 This protocol identifies the most appropriate algorithms to identify MS, in various healthcare data sources and determines the prevalence of MS in pregnant women and women of childbearing age in six European countries. The second part of the protocol addresses the utilization of medications for MS among women of childbearing age and in pregnant women. Finally, the safety study plans to address pregnancy outcomes, and specifically congenital anomalies, for women exposed to medications to treat MS during pregnancy.

4. **“Demonstrating solutions for studying intermittent medication exposures in diseases with episodic manifestations during pregnancy: application to medication for migraine in pregnancy.”** EUPAS43409 This study looks at the use of medication for migraine and more specifically its intermittent use before, during, and after pregnancy. The study also estimates the underlying prevalence of gestational diabetes and preeclampsia in this population. The safety study focuses on the use of medication for migraine and adverse maternal outcomes of gestational diabetes and preeclampsia.

5. **“Studying drug exposure when disease is measured through accurate identification of an incident case: application to breast cancer in pregnancy.”** EUPAS43393 This protocol focuses on the incidence of pregnancy associated breast cancer and non-pregnancy associated breast cancer in European countries, pregnancy outcomes, and finally the 5-year survival for women in these two groups adjusted for tumour characteristics and time of diagnosis. The pattern of treatment

for breast cancer in these populations, what medications are used and how the treatment patterns change across pregnancy was also planned to be studied.

The study protocols were uploaded to the EU PAS register and are available on the ConcePTION website (D1.3; <https://www.imi-conception.eu/results/deliverables/>). An umbrella protocol was used during the preparation of the specific protocols in order to engage with local Ethics Committees.

Face to face discussions were conducted with each data source expert for each DP to determine if participation was possible in terms of authorisations needed, funding, data sharing and available time and resources. Data characterization was performed for each potential data source to provide information on the availability and quality of individual data items (D7.14; <https://www.imi-conception.eu/results/deliverables/>). The selection was based on the suitability of the data held for the specific needs of each DP. Most data sources provided data from 2006 to 2020.

Results

1. Selecting appropriate Data Sources

Data sources from Finland, France, Italy, Norway, Spain and UK were selected for use in at least one demonstration project (Table 1). Data from EUROmediCAT provided accurate and comprehensive data on congenital anomalies occurring in 14 regions in Europe, enabling case malformed control disproportionality analyses to be completed upon linkage to medicines data. In addition to information on the coding and completeness of the variables in each data source (data characterization), local expertise was essential to obtain a full understanding of the data. Including data sources without detailed knowledge of them can lead to misleading conclusions.

Table 1: Data access providers (data sources used) in each Demonstration Project (DP)

Demonstration Project	DP1	DP2	DP3	DP4	DP5
Total number of Data Access Providers	7	6	7	5	4
Europe (EUROmediCAT Central Database)^a	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No
Finland (National health databases)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
France - Haute Garonne (EFEMERIS)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
(POMME)	No	Yes	No	No	No

Norway (National health databases)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Spain Valencia (FISABIO)	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
UK - Wales (SAIL)	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes
Italy - Emilia Romagna (Regional health databases)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No

^aUsed for safety studies only

Recommendation: In addition to using the data characterization results generated as part of the ConCePTION workflow (Add ref D7.14), collaborate with the data source experts to determine if it is affordable, adequately resourced, contains essential covariates, and is ‘fit for purpose’ before inclusion in the study. After minimal requirements for data sources are prespecified, use tools like SPIFD tool, a structured framework for conducting a step-by-step guide to identify decision grade, fit-for-purpose data, which complements the United States Food and Drug Administration (FDA)’s framework for a RWE program (Gatto et al., 2022). Consider using existing databases such as EUROmediCAT when analysing congenital anomalies. Evaluate the accuracy, completeness, and relevance of the data in relation to the study objectives.

2: Developing a Common Data Model (CDM)

When conducting medication safety studies in pregnancy across multiple data sources, adopting a common data model (CDM) can greatly facilitate multinational studies allowing all analyses to be performed using the same analysis scripts with minimal data source specific individual adaptations. However, this approach requires significant investments to map individual data sources onto the CDM. Inconsistent data mapping can lead to challenges in data integration and comparability.

Recommendation: Ensure sufficient time to map all data sources onto a CDM to harmonize syntactically and/or semantically to standardize data formats and structures *before* starting the actual multinational study. In constructing a CDM it is essential to have the users and data source experts involved as the CDM needs to be sustainable, updateable and implementable. Ensure that Extract, Transform and Load (ETL) procedures are correctly modified for each individual data source. This will facilitate easier data integration, ensure consistency across different datasets, and avoid delays.

3: Developing a Functional Data Analytical Pipeline

Conversion of real-world data from heterogeneous data sources into reliable real-world evidence on medication safety in pregnancy and breastfeeding involves many iterative steps from data characterization and harmonization, to developing study variables and algorithms and performing descriptive and analytic plans.

Recommendation: Close, reactive and proactive collaboration between data analysts/programmers, researchers and data source experts to create a multi-disciplinary team and to develop robust, functional data analytical pipelines. Ideally the data analyst/programmer should be situated within the research team and should have access to the data directly (or to synthetic data) to be able to test the analytical pipeline on data to prevent issues in later analytical steps. Ensure that all steps from data extraction to analysis are well-documented and functional to enhance reliability and transparency. When developing a pipeline, it is important to pilot demonstration projects during the developmental process and set aside sufficient time to test the pipeline with simple demonstration studies before embarking on more complex demonstration studies.

4: Developing a Pregnancy Algorithm

In medication safety studies of pregnant women using routinely collected health data, it is essential to identify pregnancy episodes and their outcomes with accurate start and end dates. Correctly identifying all pregnancies and their outcomes is very challenging and likely to be biased towards missing the shorter pregnancies with more adverse outcomes, eg. those ending in miscarriage or induced abortion.

Recommendation: A validated pregnancy algorithm that also allows reliable detection and dating of pregnancy outcomes should be adopted if it exists or developed if not. Each data source has its own characteristics, data structure and representation that could impact the validity of the pregnancy algorithm. Validity for the pregnancy algorithm should be assessed in each data source individually.

5: Developing Phenotype Algorithms

In medication safety studies involving pregnant women, accurately identifying all women with the underlying diseases indicated for the medication under investigation is crucial. This reduces the risk of confounding by indication and disease misclassification. Including details such as disease severity and subtype further enhances the accuracy of the analysis. Using medications to identify diseases can be appropriate in some cases, such as using triptans to identify migraineurs. However, in other cases, it may exacerbate indication bias, especially when the medication is prescribed for multiple

conditions, such as gabapentoids, which are used for both neuropathic pain and seizure control. Substance knowledge is essential.

Developing and validating maternal disease algorithms for a range of European health data sources is challenging. Several DPs investigated the prevalence of diseases in pregnant women (including migraine, depression, multiple sclerosis (MS) and breast cancer). The prevalences were shown to be influenced by several factors including the look-back time available at the pregnancy start and the use of period or point prevalence rates. For Migraine, disease rates were around 50% lower with 3 months lookback time versus 1 year lookback time (D1.6; <https://www.imi-conception.eu/results/deliverables/>). Variations in clinical practice and health system characteristics also influenced the estimated lookback length required to identify 95% of MS cases which was from 6 to 9 years in the different databases.

Data from hospital, primary care, specialist and prescription databases are all valuable independent sources of information with their relative importance depending on the disease, treatment or medication. Conditions such as epilepsy, anxiety and neuropathic pain are chronic conditions and long-term management is often in primary and specialized care, with few instances necessitating overnight hospitalization. Hence for these conditions only using inpatient data may not be representative.

Recommendation: Develop robust disease algorithms and compare them against known standards (if they exist) or prior studies. Employ alternative methods to validate algorithms in each data source when validation by chart review is not feasible. For example, use clinician expert panels specific to each data source to review and discuss the codes and the results of the disease algorithm. If validation is not feasible, then studies should include quantitative bias analysis to evaluate and quantify the impact of potential biases on study results. Explore the impact of look-back time for baseline rates of disease algorithms. If possible, use different sources of data (such as primary care data vs hospital data) to perform internal sensitivity analyses. Conduct benchmarking of results against prior studies using the same type of data and specify the time period of prevalence (for example 1-year prevalence). This process will help to provide context for interpreting results.

6: Assessing impact of missingness and misclassification

In medication safety studies in pregnant women using routinely collected health data from several European sources, there may be a large amount of missing data and the reasons for the missing data may not be random. These patterns of missingness may create bias in terms of

misclassification. Parameter estimates in models that account for misclassification and missing data can differ significantly from those in models that do not.

An example of this was observed in the fifth demonstration project: When analysing overall survival of women with pregnancy associated breast cancer compared with non-pregnancy associated breast cancer, women with more missing data on clinical prognostic factors had a poorer prognosis. This resulted in the complete case analysis estimates of the hazard ratio being significantly higher than the estimates based on imputed data.

Recommendation: Ensure the statistical analysis protocols include methods to assess missing data and methods to handle it, such as multiple imputation. Assess the impact of misclassification on study results using quantitative bias analysis. Perform sensitivity analyses to understand how misclassification might influence the findings. Implement strategies to minimize misclassification, such as refining case definitions and using multiple data sources to validate exposures and outcomes.

7: Handling Small Numbers

In medication safety studies with pregnant women with rare diseases, new medications or rare study outcomes, small numbers may arise in the different data sources. It is crucial to be able to fully utilize such data by aggregating from all data sources. In multinational studies different local or national restrictions and differences in definition of aggregated level data must be dealt with.

Recommendation: To allow data to be combined, ensure a secure portal is available for uploading and sharing data. Larger datasets can help identify where small numbers are likely to occur in smaller datasets. This insight can guide covariate categorization and masking low numbers, as well as inform the writing of programming script to collapse tables cells into larger categories. Potential issues related to the release of small numbers should be carefully considered during project planning. Analysis using a Bayesian Federated Inference framework should be considered (Jonker MA et al., 2024).

8: Choosing between complexity and inclusivity

When conducting medication safety studies in pregnancy using routinely collected health data across different European data sources there will be variability in the availability, accuracy and completeness of potentially important confounders.

Restricting the confounder adjustment to those only available in all data sources can lead to residual confounding due to exclusion of important information. Scaling down the number of covariates could result in a loss of information.

Recommendation: In the planning of medication safety studies, ensure included data sources have adequate data on the key covariates required for inclusion (D1.2; <https://www.imi-conception.eu/results/deliverables/>). It is necessary to balance between, on one hand, inclusion of suitable data sources with availability of covariates to address the study objectives and, on the other hand enough data sources to achieve adequate study power. Develop methods to overcome specific missing covariates in individual data sources, by using for example high dimensional propensity scores as proxies for lack of potential confounders to reduce residual confounding (e.g.: where local regulations permit the use of all patient related data). However, this approach may not be possible for data sources where data minimisation is required, and where only directly relevant covariates for overall study objectives are available in the data sources.

Another approach is to measure the impact of the confounder on the risk estimate in data sources where it is available and use this information to extrapolate or model its impact on risk estimates in data sources where it is not available. Ensure key covariates are available in at least one data source in each medication safety study.

9: Dealing with heterogeneity

Analyses of routinely collected health data across different European sources can result in heterogeneity in the prevalence of medication-exposures and diseases/outcomes. When performing safety studies, the true relative risk of adverse outcomes associated with the exposure would be expected to be the same across Europe.

In practice, a random-effects model is often preferred in meta-analyses because real-world studies typically involve some degree of heterogeneity as indicated by measures like Cochran's Q test or the I^2 statistic.

The prevalence of medication exposure may vary significantly between data sources due to differences in prescription guidelines across countries. Therefore, producing an overall European prevalence may not be appropriate. Providing the range of prevalences is considered more appropriate than a meta-analysis of prevalence rates. An investigation of the differences in prevalence between the data sources is considered more informative.

Recommendation: The expertise and local knowledge provided by the data access providers is necessary to ensure correct interpretation of the heterogeneity and overall results. To explore real differences in associations, ensure the consortium includes data from both affluent and less affluent countries, as assessed by GDP per capita.

10. Influencing clinical practice using evidence from medication safety studies in pregnancy and breastfeeding

Reliable evidence generated from robust scientific medication safety studies in pregnancy using real-world data can have important implications for clinical practice as it enables pregnant women and health care providers to make informed treatment decisions.

Recommendation: It is important to consult clinical experts in the planning and execution of the studies to ensure that the results can be used in clinical practice. Findings should be presented in a clear, actionable format. Collaborating with stakeholders is imperative to ensure that research outcomes inform clinical decisions and regulatory policies.

Discussion and Conclusion

Multinational real world perinatal pharmaco-epidemiological studies are essential for understanding the impact of medication use on maternal and child health.

Data sources suitable for medication safety studies in pregnancy are those that individually, or when linked, provide high quality data (in terms of accuracy, completeness, reliability, relevance and timelines) on (i) gestational age-specific exposure to medication; (ii) outcomes for mother and/or foetus/infant/child; (iii) potential confounders, including confounding by indication. Maternal and child health studies are unique in requiring linkage between data relating to the mother, and data relating to the infant. The quality and completeness of that linkage is paramount.

A multidisciplinary collaborative team is essential, providing in-depth knowledge of all data sources and fostering responsive interactions throughout the study. This approach is critical from study conception to applying the results in clinical practice

Collaborative, innovative, and patient-centred approaches will be key to advancing the field and improving health outcomes in pregnancy globally. By addressing methodological challenges and leveraging innovative approaches to federated pregnancy and breastfeeding studies, we can enhance the quality and impact of perinatal pharmaco-epidemiological research in Europe and

globally.

By learning from past experiences and implementing these recommendations, future research can achieve greater accuracy, relevance, and impact.

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